

Data Sharing Agreement Development Guidelines

Australian Research Data Commons

January 2023

With the exception of logos and third-party materials or where otherwise indicated, this work is licensed under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Contents

Contents	1
Document Purpose	3
What Is a Data Sharing Agreement?	3
When Are Data Sharing Agreements Needed?	3
Common Types of Data Sharing Agreements	4
Common Components of a Data Sharing Agreement	4
Information about the data, parties and context of the agreement	5
Conditions of sharing	6
Additional sections or areas in the contract document	8
Creating a Data Sharing Agreement	10
When to Start Developing a Data Sharing Agreement	10
Summary	12
Glossary	14

Document Purpose

This document provides guidance for those who are developing a data sharing agreement. Data sharing agreements are agreements entered into by two (or more) entities who are sharing and receiving data. This document will help those wishing to share the data and those wanting to access the data understand when a data sharing agreement is required, what is typically covered in it, and how you should go about producing it.

What Is a Data Sharing Agreement?

A data sharing agreement (DSA) is an agreement between two or more entities (most likely legal entities) that are providing and receiving data. The agreement is often made between two or more researchers (i.e. individuals) who are sharing or accessing the data. These researchers are often not the legal owners of the data, and the entities signing the DSA are actually the organisations they work for (though they may have delegation to sign the agreement on behalf of their organisations).

A DSA specifies the conditions under which the data will be shared. It documents what can and cannot be done with the data, giving clarity and certainty to all parties. The document can be seen as a set of rules around how the data can be accessed, shared, and reused. Creating a DSA helps the data provider meet their legal and ethical obligations to protect the data from accidental misuse. It can also protect the rights of the data custodians and provide clarity on data usage for the recipient of the data. Although a DSA does not have a strict legal definition, the majority of DSAs are written as a legal contract (either binding or non-binding).

When Are Data Sharing Agreements Needed?

It is always important that potential reusers of data understand the terms and conditions for reuse. However, it is not always necessary for the data provider and reuser to negotiate, draft, and sign an agreement – the terms and conditions can be stated in such other ways as verbal communication and agreement. Whether a DSA is required will depend on the nature of the data, the risks present in the sharing of the data, and the complexity of the conditions under which the data can be shared.

For instance, some data providers are able to make their data openly accessible for reuse. Often there are relatively straightforward conditions that apply to anyone who accesses the data. These conditions can include the requirement that the data only be used for non-commercial purposes or that the provider be attributed in any output derived from the data. In this case, the same conditions apply to

anyone who accesses the data, so there is no need to negotiate a specific agreement for every case of reuse. The provider will usually place a licence on the data that the reuser implicitly agrees to by accessing the data, e.g. a [Creative Commons License](#).

A DSA between the parties is more often used when the data is sensitive and access is only granted to certain projects on request. This is because a DSA allows the provider and requester to agree upon the terms and conditions specific to the particular context in which the data is shared.

Common Types of Data Sharing Agreements

There is no single standard format or template for a DSA, but they typically take the form of a legally binding contract between the relevant entities. The contents of a DSA will be tailored to the needs of the data provider and requester and to the details of the project. The kinds of information typically included in a DSA are listed in the next section.

Common agreement types are:

- agreements covering one-off data sharing – these can arise when, for instance, a researcher requests access to a specific existing dataset for a research project
- agreements covering ongoing data sharing between entities – an example of this kind of data sharing is that between a medical research institute and a university as part of the activities of a medical research network. These agreements are sometimes referred to as “data sharing accords”. They are often seen when organisations form long-term partnerships with each other with the intent of sharing the respective ongoing data collections. The sharing of some data between partners may still be subject to case-by-case review and approval, such as to negotiate authorship rights, but the utility of an accord is to pre-determine the partners’ general requirements regarding issues such as licence, commercialisation, and data security.

Common Components of a Data Sharing Agreement

The contents of a DSA will depend on the needs of the parties and the details of the data and the project. However, the components below are commonly included in a DSA and are a good starting point for those drafting a DSA without an existing template. This is not an exhaustive list, and not all sections listed here will be necessary for all DSAs.

Information about the data, parties and context of the agreement

Details of the data to be shared

- Clear descriptions of the data that will be shared so that there is no ambiguity about what data the agreement refers to
- Where needed, the agreement may specify the fields to be included, the time period or geographic region covered, the resolution of the data, etc.

Purpose of the data sharing

- Specifications of why the data is being shared (e.g. the research project in which the data will be used)

Period of the agreement

- Statements of when the agreement begins and ends
- The conditions of the agreement may refer to these dates. For instance, the data provider may be required to inform the data receiver of any corrections or updates to the original dataset during the period of the agreement, or the data receiver may be required to delete all copies of the dataset at the end of the agreement.

Parties to the agreement

- Specifications of the entities who are entering into the agreement, i.e. the data provider(s) and the data receiver(s)
- Note that it is important to be clear who has the ability to agree to the terms specified in the DSA. In some cases, the parties could be the data custodian and the requesting researcher, but very often the parties to the agreement must be the research organisations rather than individuals. (See the section "[What Is a Data Sharing Agreement?](#)".)

Roles and responsibilities

- It may be necessary to specify roles as part of the agreement. This could be because the agreement requires that a specific person be nominated as responsible for performing particular tasks, such as managing the data transfer or reporting back on project outcomes. The agreement could also place restrictions on who can do certain things with the data once it is received. For instance, the data provider might require that only the lead investigator be allowed access to

personal identifiers in the data and that others on the project be allowed to access only non-identifying versions of the data

- If roles form part of the agreement, then the DSA may specify who holds these roles. If specific individuals are named, it is also important to state what happens if they leave the project and how new individuals are to be appointed to those roles

Conditions of sharing

Requirements can be placed on both the data requester and the data provider with regard to the following:

Permitted use of the data

- The purpose for which the data may be used by the requester and, where relevant, restrictions on commercial use

Allowed or prohibited processing or analyses

- It may be necessary to prohibit certain kinds of processing of the data, such as attempts to combine the data with other datasets that will re-identify individuals

Sensitivity of the data

- Including any risks that are present in the data and how they should be managed
- Data that warrants such conditions can include identifiable human data, sensitive cultural information, and data about endangered species.

Existing constraints on the data

- Current (legal) restrictions that apply to the data and must be complied with by the requester, such as state privacy legislation
- There might also be specific policy conditions to adhere to. The ARDC has [guidelines on developing data sharing policies](#), which can support policy decisions.

Confidentiality

- Restrictions on the disclosure of the data, or information about the data, to third parties by the requester

Derived data

- Ownership of and restrictions on any datasets derived from the shared data

Research outputs

- Restrictions on the outputs of the project, such as the requirement that statistics be reported at a certain level of aggregation so that sensitive information is not unintentionally disclosed
- The data provider may require that they review outputs before they are made public.

Data security

- Security-related restrictions on the requester's handling of the data, including those on storage, access control, analysis environments, and the transfer of the data

Retention and disposal of the data

- Any requirements for how the data must be handled after the end of the project, including those for the destruction of the data

Changes and corrections

- What the provider agrees to do if there are any changes or corrections to the original dataset after it is provided to the requester. This could include notifying the requester and providing the updated data within a particular timeframe

Reporting of incidental findings

Costs associated with the data sharing

- Who is responsible for meeting any costs associated with sharing the data

Method of access

- Method(s) by which the data will be made available to the requester – methods can include transferring the data to the requester, granting access to the data within the provider’s own systems, and making the data available at a secure virtual or physical location

Format of the data

- The file format in which the data will be provided
- Information about other aspects of the data format, such as any pre-processing, cleaning, or linkage of the data

Timing of the data sharing

- The date by which the data must be made available by the provider
- For data updated at regular intervals, timing of the ongoing sharing

Support for the data sharing

- Contact details of anyone supporting the data sharing process

Signoff for the DSA

- Details of those who sign off the agreement, who are most likely the data custodian and the requester of the data (researcher)
- Input from the legal and research office or equivalent to ensure compliance
- Date of the agreement or document
- Contact details of the signatories.

Additional sections or areas in the contract document

The following are some additional elements that might be included or covered in the DSA. Some of these relate back to items listed above, but for clarity they are mentioned here again:

Title

- The DSA will require a title that describes the data request accordingly.
- A brief description of the title could also be provided for context.

Licence and copyright and intellectual property

- Details of any licences or copyright conditions should be expressed. These may be related to specific data being shared that is outside the scope of the DSA.
- Comments on potential commercial use of the data need to be expressed. Generally, requests for data will be made for continued research purposes, but they may also be made for commercial purposes, which will need to be detailed and agreed upon.
- Recognition of authorship and/or custodianship is key to licensing and should be discussed. Attribution should be added to the data when it is reused.

Reporting requirements

- There may be specific reporting requirements attached to the data being shared.

Variations in the data

- If any variation in the data occurs during the process of requesting the data, it needs to be recorded.
- Data modifications need to be noted.

Risks

- List any potential risks that the sharing of the data might involve. This may depend on the sensitivity of the data, the nature of the data, and the way in which it is being shared and handled.
- Undertake a risk assessment.

Termination

- The agreement should deal with the circumstances around its termination, stating what behaviours might lead to its being terminated and the data sharing being stopped (e.g. misuse of the data).

Creating a Data Sharing Agreement

It is important that all relevant individuals (data owners, custodians, requesters) are involved in the creation of a DSA. Creation of a DSA may also be influenced by the rights and responsibilities of the institutions that employ the data providers and the data requesters. It could be that the institution holds intellectual property rights over the data that must be protected. It could also be that the institution is at risk of being held legally or financially responsible if the data is mismanaged or misused. If this is the case, appropriate delegates of the institution must be consulted in the development of the DSA. Ideally, an institution will have policy or guidelines in place to make it clear when the institution must be involved in the creation of DSAs. If no such policy is in place, the best practice is to check with the research office and/or legal department. Institutions may already have developed or consider developing a DSA template for researchers who wish to share or reuse data.

Creating a DSA is typically a process of negotiation between the entities' legal representatives (with the input from relevant institutional stakeholders on both sides) to ensure that the conditions of the agreement meet the needs of both parties. The negotiation between the custodian and the requester normally precedes the DSA and happens at the data request stage. This may require many rounds of revisions, particularly if the conditions are complex. It usually takes place following an Expression of Interest (EOI) or data request for accessing and reusing the data.

As mentioned, some institutions provide DSA templates. These templates help streamline the process of developing a DSA by ensuring that the agreement covers aspects of the data sharing deemed necessary by the institution. They may provide pre-approved wording for particular sections. Note that the requester's institution may not agree with one or more sections of the provider's template and may request amendments to the draft DSA before signing as is common before signing any contract. DSA templates are useful in that they document the data provider's default position regarding the use of their data and provide a solid starting point for data custodians seeking to share data.

When to Start Developing a Data Sharing Agreement

As mentioned, developing a DSA can require considerable negotiation and many rounds of revisions. It can take a long time, particularly if the data to be shared is complex and, say, highly sensitive. It is therefore important that the development of a DSA begins as soon as possible to avoid unnecessary delays in the project for which the data is requested.

It is also important to develop a DSA early in a project needing data for reuse. This is because the conditions under which the data is shared may impact many aspects of the project's planning. For

instance, the conditions of a DSA could limit who on the team is allowed to access the data, where it can be stored and analysed, what analyses may be conducted, and how the outputs of the research may be communicated. If these factors are not understood and taken into account early in the project, they may cause serious problems for the success of the project later on.

DSAs are typically developed when a request is made to access the data. It can, however, be beneficial for data holders planning to make their data available for reuse to consider the terms and conditions for its sharing in advance of any request. Remember that the data may be requested long after the end of the project that first generated it. It is important that any initial conditions placed on its reuse (say, as a result of ethics approval or legal restrictions) are clearly documented so that future requests for the data are handled appropriately. It is also important to understand who on the project has the authority to approve reuse requests and enter into a DSA with the requester. These are all key to good data governance.

The diagram below illustrates when and where in the research data management life cycle the development of a DSA might be considered. For a primary research project, data sharing may be discussed as part of the ethics process. Meanwhile, for a secondary research project, where the data already exists, the sharing of the data may be discussed later on in the project.

Figure 1 (next page): The data management life cycle. Sharing of data needs to be considered at the “Create or Receive” and “Access, Use and Reuse” stages. (Diagram courtesy of [the Digital Curation Centre](#))

Summary

This document has outlined the considerations and components associated with the creation of a data sharing agreement (DSA), a document required to allow for sound and legal sharing of data.

In summary, the creation of a DSA follows these steps:

1. Determine whether a DSA is required. This is often achieved following the application of an Expression of Interest (EOI) for accessing or reusing the data (i.e. a data request). The EOI will be

assessed for the level of the access request to see if a DSA is needed or whether the data can be shared without one.

2. If a DSA is required, the data custodian and the data requester (researcher) will have discussions to determine why the requester wants access to the data and how it will potentially be reused. These details will be recorded in the DSA.
3. Terms and conditions (T&Cs) are then discussed in relation to the access and reuse of the data. These are also documented in the DSA.
4. The T&Cs should be discussed with the legal office and/or the research office within the institution or organisation to ensure they are feasible and appropriate. The T&Cs can be determined using [the list of common components of a DSA](#) provided in this document.
5. Once the DSA has been finalised and the content agreed, the relevant parties can sign the document (contract).
6. The requested data can be shared according to the conditions set out in the DSA.

In conclusion, a DSA documents the terms and conditions of sharing and reusing data between two or more parties and articulates each party's rights and responsibilities. While the concept of a DSA is not defined in legislation, many DSAs are written as legal contracts and must be approached with due consideration. It is recommended that anyone looking to draft or sign a DSA seek guidance from their institution or employer.

Glossary

The following glossary explains some of the key terms in this document:

Table 1. Glossary of key terms in this document

TERM(S)	DESCRIPTION
Data sharing agreement (DSA)	A data sharing agreement (DSA) is a formal agreement between a data provider and a data requester that refers to a specific case of data sharing. A DSA typically takes the form of a binding contract between the two parties. It clearly documents the terms and conditions under which the data are being shared.
Data sharing policy	A data sharing policy is a policy written by an organisation or group to address the types of data the agencies have in their custody, the principles and strategy around the sharing of that data, and the governance and management procedures that should be followed when that data is being shared. It lays out, in general terms, how that organisation or group will respond to requests to share the data.
Entity	An entity is one or more persons or organisations responsible for the management of the research data, namely the provider or the requester.
Data custodian, data provider, data owner	The person or organisation who owns the data and is responsible for sharing it.
Data requester, data receiver, data recipient	The person or organisation asking to access the data.
Institution or organisation	The organisation or group of individuals who own

	or request the data.
Stakeholders	The other people within an organisation or institution who may have a role or an interest in the request and sharing of the data but do not have a specific role in the completion of the DSA.